

High-Output Para-Hisian Pacing to Differentiate Far-Field from Near-Field His-Bundle Potentials in a Patient with Atrioventricular Nodal Reentrant Tachycardia

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ABSTRACT

Background: Atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia (AVNRT) is typically treated via slow pathway ablation. However, when the circuit involves atypical superior insertions or mid-septal anatomy, the risk of atrioventricular (AV) block increases. Precise differentiation between near-field and far-field His-bundle potentials is crucial to ensure a safe ablation margin.

Methods: We report a case of a 19-year-old patient with highly inducible AVNRT. Conventional ablation at the anatomical slow pathway area and coronary sinus ostium failed to eliminate the arrhythmia. Mapping revealed a signal resembling a His-bundle potential at a mid-septal site, 1 cm inferior to the documented His position. To characterize this signal, high-output pacing (10.0 mA) was performed from the ablation catheter to differentiate myocardial capture from selective His-bundle capture by analyzing QRS morphology and stimulus-to-ventricular latency.

Results: High-output pacing identified the signal as a "far-field" His potential. Radiofrequency delivery at this site immediately induced sustained junctional rhythms without AV conduction impairment. Post-ablation testing confirmed non-inducibility of the tachycardia, a persistent AH jump with only one echo beat, and preserved AV conduction (final AH 70 ms, HV 30 ms). No complications occurred.

Conclusion: In cases where conventional anatomical approaches are ineffective, high-output para-Hisian pacing allows for the safe identification of atypical slow pathway insertion sites. This maneuver effectively differentiates near-field from far-field His signals, minimizing the risk of permanent AV block.

KEYWORDS: *Atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia*, Catheter ablation, Para-Hisian pacing, Slow pathway ablation, Electrophysiological study.

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INTRODUCTION

Atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia (AVNRT) is the most common supraventricular tachycardia in adults and is characterized by a reentry circuit involving dual atrioventricular (AV) nodal pathways [1,2]. Radiofrequency catheter ablation of the slow pathway is the gold-standard treatment, with reported success rates exceeding 95% [2]. Despite its high efficacy, complete AV block remains the most significant complication, particularly in patients with

variant nodal anatomy or when the slow pathway is located in close proximity to the His bundle and compact AV node [3].

Precise localization of safe ablation zones is therefore critical. Para-Hisian pacing is a well-established electrophysiological maneuver designed to differentiate His-bundle capture from local myocardial capture and assess proximity to the AV conduction system [4]. While this technique has been extensively validated in the evaluation of accessory

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pathways, its application as a safety-guiding tool during AVNRT ablation has been less frequently described [5]. We present a case in which high-output para-Hisian pacing was instrumental in distinguishing near-field from far-field His-bundle signals, allowing for safe and effective ablation in an atypical mid-septal location [6–8].

CASE PRESENTATION

A 19-year-old patient presented for an electrophysiological study (EPS) due to recurrent palpitations. Baseline intervals were: AH 60 ms and HV 35 ms. The AV nodal effective refractory period (AVNERP) was 220 ms, and the Wenckebach point was 320 ms, showing concentric and decremental retrograde conduction.

Mechanical contact with the catheters easily induced a narrow QRS tachycardia with a cycle length (CL) of 250 ms and a VA interval of 60 ms, consistent with typical AVNRT (Fig 1 and Fig 2). Programmed ventricular stimulation confirmed concentric and decremental retrograde conduction, effectively ruling out a retrogradely conducting accessory pathway (Fig 3). This was further corroborated by a formal para-Hisian pacing maneuver, which showed a prolongation of the VA interval (Δ VA 18 ms) upon losing His-bundle capture (Fig 4).

Initial radiofrequency (RF) ablation attempts were performed at conventional anatomical sites, including the inferior right and left slow pathway areas, the coronary sinus (CS) ostium, and the proximal portion of the CS. These applications failed to elicit junctional beats or modify the circuit.

Mapping was subsequently performed more superiorly. Approximately 1 cm inferior to the documented His-bundle position, the ablation catheter recorded a signal morphology similar to a His potential but with a less sharp, more "blunted" appearance (Fig 5). To determine the nature of this signal, high-output pacing (10.0 mA) was performed. Pacing from the diagnostic His catheter showed direct His-bundle capture with a short Target-to-Intrinsic Deflection Interval (TIDI) of 66 ms (Fig 6). In contrast, pacing from the ablation catheter at the target site demonstrated pure myocardial capture with a wider QRS and a TIDI of 100 ms (Fig 7). This differentiation identified the ablation catheter signal as a "far-field" His potential, providing a safe margin for RF delivery. During RF application at this specific mid-septal site, sustained junctional rhythms were immediately observed for 60 seconds with preserved 1:1 VA conduction (Fig 8). Post-ablation programmed stimulation revealed a persistent AH jump with only a single echo beat, but no inducible tachycardia. Final measurements remained stable (AH 70 ms, HV 32 ms, AVNERP < 200 ms) (Fig 9).

DISCUSSION

The primary challenge in AVNRT ablation lies in the anatomical proximity of the slow pathway to the specialized conduction system, particularly in cases with atypical or

superior pathway insertions [3,7]. In the present case, failure of ablation at conventional inferior sites suggested a mid-septal slow pathway location.

Ablation in para-Hisian or mid-septal regions is associated with an increased risk of inadvertent AV block [6]. Our case illustrates how high-output para-Hisian pacing, traditionally used to differentiate retrograde conduction mechanisms, can be repurposed as a safety maneuver during AVNRT ablation [4,8]. By comparing QRS morphology and capture latency during pacing at 10.0 mA, we were able to definitively classify the recorded signal as far-field, thereby enabling ablation in a high-risk region while preserving AV nodal integrity.

In young patients, in whom the long-term consequences of pacemaker dependency are particularly significant, the use of meticulous mapping strategies such as para-Hisian pacing should be considered a valuable adjunct when conventional anatomical approaches are unsuccessful [7,8].

STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Competing Interests

The authors have no financial or non-financial interests that are directly or indirectly related to the work submitted for publication.

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Figure legends:

Fig 1. Twelve-lead electrocardiogram during tachycardia. A narrow QRS complex tachycardia is observed with a cycle length of 361 ms. The tracing demonstrates a short-RP relationship (RP < PR) with an RP interval of 60 ms and 1:1 ventriculoatrial (VA) conduction. A characteristic pseudo r' wave in lead V1 is present.

Fig 2. Intracardiac electrograms during tachycardia. The tracing shows a narrow QRS complex tachycardia with a stable cycle length (CL) of 253 ms (237 bpm). Ventriculoatrial (VA) conduction is concentric and decremental, with the earliest atrial activation recorded at the Coronary Sinus (CS) ostium. A short VA interval of 64 ms is measured from the onset of ventricular activation to the earliest atrial signal, confirming a diagnosis of typical atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia

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Fig 3. Programmed ventricular stimulation. The intracardiac recordings demonstrate concentric and decremental retrograde conduction. The earliest atrial activation is consistently recorded at the His-bundle and proximal coronary sinus (CS) regions. The decremental response observed during ventricular extrastimuli pacing (S1-S2) effectively rules out the presence of a retrogradely conducting accessory pathway, confirming that retrograde conduction occurs exclusively via the atrioventricular node.

Fig 4. Para-Hisian pacing maneuver for accessory pathway exclusion. Selective His-bundle capture (QRS duration 118 ms) results in a ventriculoatrial (VA) interval of 118 ms. Upon losing His capture, pure myocardial capture (QRS duration 136 ms) occurs, which leads to an increase in the VA interval to 136 ms. This prolongation of the VA interval (Δ VA 18 ms) following the loss of His-bundle capture, while maintaining a concentric atrial activation sequence, definitively excludes a retrogradely conducting septal accessory pathway and confirms retrograde conduction via the atrioventricular node.

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Fig 5. Intracardiac electrogram comparison at the mid-septal ablation site. The ablation catheter (ABL D) records a signal morphology resembling a His-bundle potential. However, when compared to the reference His-bundle catheter (HIS D), the ABL signal appears less "sharp" and more "blunted," suggesting a far-field recording of the conduction system. This ambiguity necessitated the use of high-output pacing to confirm a safe distance from the compact AV node before radiofrequency delivery

Fig 6. High-output pacing (10.0 mA) from the diagnostic His-bundle catheter. In contrast to the ablation site, pacing from this location results in direct His-bundle capture, evidenced by a narrow QRS complex and a characteristic latency between the stimulus and ventricular activation. The measured Target-to-Intrinsic Deflection Interval (TIDI) of 66 ms is significantly shorter than the 100 ms interval observed at the ablation site, definitively distinguishing near-field His-bundle contact from the far-field signals identified at the successful mid-septal ablation target.

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Fig 7. High-output pacing (10.0 mA) from the ablation catheter at the target mid-septal site. The pacing maneuver demonstrates pure myocardial capture characterized by a wide QRS morphology (120 ms) and the absence of stimulus-to-ventricular latency. The measured Target-to-Intrinsic Deflection Interval (TIDI) of 100 ms further confirms that the catheter is localized within the septal myocardium and not in direct contact with the His-bundle or its immediate branches. These findings provided the electrophysiological confirmation needed to safely proceed with radiofrequency delivery at this location.

Fig 8. Radiofrequency (RF) catheter ablation at the target mid-septal site. The vertical purple bar in the center of the tracing marks the onset of RF delivery. After 6 seconds of application, sustained junctional rhythms (nodal beats) are observed, confirming effective modification of the slow pathway substrate. Throughout the application, 1:1 ventriculoatrial conduction was monitored (as seen in the HRA and HIS channels), ensuring the functional integrity of the compact atrioventricular node and the absence of high-grade AV block.

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Fig 9. Final electrophysiological measurements post-ablation. The intracardiac recordings demonstrate stable baseline intervals with a preserved HV interval of 32 ms. Programmed atrial stimulation confirmed the successful modification of the reentry substrate, with a significantly shortened atrioventricular nodal effective refractory period (AVNERP) of < 200 ms. No inducible tachycardia or sustained echo beats were observed during aggressive programmed stimulation, confirming a successful clinical endpoint.